

INTERACTIVE MEDIA QUALITY BY USING CONSTRUCTIVE APPROACH TO PHYSICAL LEARNING

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Abstract

The background of this study is the lack of availability of interactive media with a constructivist approach to physics learning, especially for light material. This study aims to produce interactive media by using constructivist approaches to physics learning for valid, practical, and effective light material. This research is a development research by using the 4D model. This research does several steps, such as define, design, develop, and disseminate. The develop phase consists of the validity test stage to see the quality of interactive media, practicality, and effectiveness. The data were obtained through validation sheets, practicality questionnaires, and effectiveness. The validity test result is 87.4% which shows very valid. The result of the practicality test is 89.0% which shows it is very practical, and the effectiveness test is 88.5% with a very effective category. Thus, interactive media with constructivist approaches to light material developed are valid, practical, and effective for use in physics learning.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System states that the function of national education is to develop abilities and form dignified national character and civilization in order to educate the life of the nation. Therefore, education in Indonesia always innovates, including using technology as a learning medium. One technology that can be used as a learning media is computers. The use of computers as learning media can help students and teachers in learning, because the computer is patient, careful, has perfect memory, computers are very flexible in learning, and can be arranged according to their own desires¹⁶. Computer-based teaching is the use of computers as a medium for delivering information on learning, practice questions, feedback or scores on student answers. The use of computers in learning is in the form of making interactive media. The Australian journal of educational technology) mentions "Interactive media could be defined as any media which the user has more than a minimum button control over what appears on the screen"¹⁷. Based on this understanding, it can be concluded that interactive media is a medium that can be used by users where users can use the control buttons on the screen.

This computer-based interactive media can be developed to help the learning process, especially in physics learning. Physics learning has its own characteristics rather than other sciences. The physics learning process has two dimensions, such as learning science material and how to do science activities¹⁸. Student processes in learning include: internalizing values, assessing oneself, and making choices through studying physics, physics careers, applying

¹⁶ Nasution. 2004. P27

¹⁷ Kearney. 2001. P674-79

¹⁸ Supriyono. 2003. p8

knowledge, and scientific skills in everyday life. Judging from the aspects of competency to be achieved, physics subjects emphasize mastery of concepts in addition to the skills to complete formulas.

The basic competencies that students must understand in physics are to investigate the properties of light and its relationship to various forms of mirrors and lenses. Based on the contents of the material, light material is abstract. The material cannot be seen and felt directly by students. To understand light material, students need imaginary power. Therefore, the use of computers in physics learning especially light material can enhance the role of students to follow physics learning and understand light matter quickly.

The constructivist approach is a learning medium that is developed with certain approaches, and one of the effective approaches. The constructivism approach is an approach that allows students to develop their understanding¹⁹. Constructivism learning is student-centered learning (student oriented) while teachers as mediators, facilitators, and learning resources in learning. Constructivist oriented learning emphasizes its own active, creative, and productive understanding through meaningful learning processes. The constructivist approach helps students build their own knowledge based on the knowledge they already have. Therefore, students will be accustomed to thinking for themselves in problem solving, independent, critical, creative, and able to be rationally responsible and not feel bored to learn.

Based on the description above, the researcher conducted a research on the development of interactive media for light material on physics learning with a constructivist approach. The development of this media is also complemented by guidelines for learning implementation design (RPP).

II. METHOD

This research is a development research. This study will develop interactive media with a constructivist approach to light material that is valid, practical, and effective, and according to the conditions and needs of students. The development model used is the 4-D model which consists of four stages, such as define, design, develop, and spread (disseminate).

At the defining stage, researchers conduct curriculum analysis, student analysis, and concept analysis. At this stage, interactive media design is designed based on the results from the define stage. The purpose of this stage is to produce revised learning products based on several experts. The next step is developing. This stage includes product validation from experts and simulations, such as activities to operationalize products²⁰. This development phase also carried out practicality tests and effectiveness of the interactive media developed. This is done so that interactive media with constructivist approaches are tested for validity, practicality, and effectiveness.

The type of data in this study is primary data. Data is taken based on the results of validation of the learning device carried out by the validator, practical data from the teacher and students, and from the results of observation and evaluation of student learning outcomes. The instruments used to collect data in this study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The Instrument of Data Collection

No	Kriteria	Instrumen
1	Validation	✓ The validation of lesson plan sheet ✓ The validation of interactive media sheet

¹⁹ Nizarwati. 2009. P58

²⁰ Trianto. 2012. P95

No	Kriteria	Instrumen
		✓ The validation of cognitive assessment sheet
2	Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ The questionnaire of students' responds on practical of interactive media ✓ The questionnaire of teachers' responds on practical of interactive media
3	Effectiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ The questionnaire of students' responds on the effectiveness of media ✓ The questionnaire of teachers' responds on the effectiveness of media ✓ The questionnaire about students' motivation ✓ The observation sheet of students' learning activities ✓ The questions sheet of cognitive assessment

The used of data analyses is :

$$V = \frac{X}{Y} \times 100 \% \quad (1)$$

V is validity/practical score, and X is a score that is obtained, and Y is a maximum score²¹. The validity of interactive media is based on the final score which can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. The Categories of Validation

Interval	Categories
0-20 %	Very Invalid/ Practical
21-40 %	Invalid/Practical
41-60 %	Less Valid/Practical
61-80 %	Valid/Practical
81-100 %	Very Valid/Practical

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The following are the results of research related to the quality of learning devices:

A. Interactive Media Validity

The results of this study are an interactive media product with a constructivist approach equipped with RPP to control learning. Each product is validated twice. Even though in the first validation it was stated that the product was very valid, the five validators still suggested that the product was better designed. In the second validation, the validator does not provide a value. After being revised, the product checks again by the validator and can be tested. After being tested, the average validation percentage was 87.5% for RPP, 87.4% for media, and 89.5% for cognitive assessment.

B. Product Practicality

Product practicality is obtained by using questionnaire responses from teachers to product practicality. The average practicality percentage obtained from the teacher's

²¹ Riduwan. 2012. P89

response was 89.0%. The average percentage of practicality obtained from student responses is 87.95%. This percentage shows that interactive media with a constructivist approach to the designed light material are very practical.

C. Product Effectiveness

The effectiveness of the product is obtained by using a teacher response questionnaire and student response questionnaire on the effectiveness of the product. The percentage of the average value of effectiveness obtained was 88.5% of the teacher's response and 95.45% of the student's response. This interactive media with constructivists is also effective in increasing student motivation and cognitive competence of students. The percentage for motivation was 89.93%, student activity at the first meeting was 83%, student activity at the second meeting was 85.5%. While cognitive achievement of students is 87.5% complete, with an average value of 88.9.

If this is compared to the media that is often used by teachers, the media with a constructivist approach that has been developed are more effective in increasing student motivation and activity during learning and also effective to improve students' cognitive competence in understanding light material. This increase in students' cognitive competence is caused by interactive media with this constructivist approach helping students construct their knowledge gradually, providing learning experiences in the form of physical and non-physical activities. The existences of this learning experience, students become more focused on learning, so that learning material is easily understood by students.

This interactive media with constructivists gets very practical and effective values when used in physics learning because it is influenced by several factors. One of them is based on the opinion of that the benefits of learning media are to make the learning process more interesting and interactive²². The media developed can stimulate students to follow learning because in the design of media, it has been adjusted to the characteristics of students. Like a combination of colors made inconspicuous, namely light blue, light green, and pink. Interactive media also comes with a button tone that makes students like playing games. So that learning physics with interactive media with this constructivist approach can eliminate students' saturation in learning physics and students are more active in learning.

Physical learning with interactive media with constructivist approaches is also in accordance with the teacher's task in constructivist learning. Anurrahman concluded that the teacher's task in constructivist's view is to provide a learning experience, provide activities that stimulate students' curiosity and help them express their ideas, teachers monitor, evaluate and show whether students' thoughts can be actively encouraged²³. Learning experiences that have been presented in the media make students more quickly understand light material

The steps of constructivist approaches that have been incorporated into interactive media can help students in constructing their understanding of light material gradually. So that it can increase student learning motivation, student activity during learning, and student cognitive competence. During the learning process, students can get a learning experience. Animation and video assistance in the media making it easier for students to imagine abstract material with light material.

Based on the results, it can be concluded that this interactive media can achieve from the learning media. The purpose of learning media is to facilitate the learning process in the classroom, improve the efficiency of the learning process, maintain the relevance between subject

²² Samodra. 2008

²³ Anurrahman. 2009. P23

matter and learning objectives and help students concentrate in the learning process²⁴. Therefore, interactive media with this constructivist approach can deal with the problems of teachers in physics learning especially for learning light that is abstract.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the development and trial, it can be concluded that the validation results of the validators show that interactive media with a constructivist approach is very valid, very practical, and very effective.

Based on the research, the following are suggested.

1. Conducting trials in several schools to get maximum results
2. Develop interactive media with a constructivist approach to other physical materials.

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²⁴ Sanaky. 2011. P4

